

β -Diketones in Ring Formation. Part I.

BY UMAPRASANNA BASU.

From a study on the condensation of certain β -diketones with cyanoacetamide, Bardhan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2223) claims that the methylene group of cyanoacetamide reacts with the keto-form of the dicarbonyl compound. But while investigating the behaviour of 2-acetylcyclohexanone and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate in several condensation reactions (Sen and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 51; 1929, 6, 309; 1930, 7, 435), it was noticed that these reactions could be better represented by the enolic than the ketonic formula (*cf.* also Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347). It was consequently considered to be of interest to examine critically the mechanism of the reaction of $\alpha\gamma$ -dicarbonyl compounds with cyanoacetamide.

At first it may be held that the initial product of such condensation would be an intermediate aldol (III), whether cyanoacetamide reacts with the enolic (I) or the ketonic form (II) of the dicarbonyl compound, thus:—

The intermediate aldol then readily passes into a pyridone derivative (IV) owing to the tendency for the formation of a six-membered ring. It is a difficult problem to distinguish between these two types of reaction, one a Michael and the other an aldol, as both are fundamentally additive in character. So the present investigation was

undertaken to determine the relative reactivities of the carbonyl group and the ethylenic linkage in β -diketones as indicated above.

It is well-known that carbonyl groups are normally associated with a high reactivity towards sodium bisulphite, potassium cyanide, hydroxylamine, phenylhydrazine, and also substances containing a reactive methylene group, but are almost inert towards halogens, ozone, and potassium permanganate, whereas the ethylenic linkage readily responds to the latter reagents but show no appreciable reactivity towards the former ones. However in a system of the type $-\dot{C}=\text{CHX}$, that is, when an ethylenic linkage occurs in the α -position with respect to a so-called negative group ($\text{X}=\text{CO}\cdot\text{R}$, CO_2Et etc.), its reactivity is considerably enhanced as shown by its behaviour even towards reagents of the former type (the ketonic reagents). A β -diketone when represented by the enolic formula (I) is a system of this type and as such it readily reacts with ozone, halogens, as well as with hydroxylamine, phenylhydrazine, etc. Hence it will not be unreasonable to expect a reactive methylene group to react with the ethylenic linkage present in the system. When, however, the ethylenic bond contains further a contiguous hydroxyl group (as in I), the presence of which enormously increases the additive capacity of the double linking (Meyer, *Annalen*, 1913, 398, 66), a preferential addition at the ethylenic linkage becomes more probable. It is on such consideration, that the view hereinafter expressed is based, that is, the enolic phase of the β -diketone, being an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl compound, will readily undergo Michael reaction with the methylene group of cyanoacetamide (Michael, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2126; Vorländer, *ibid.* p. 2053; *Annalen*, 1897, 294, 267; Scheiber and Meisel, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 238; Thorpe and Norris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1201; Kon and collaborators, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 125, 1361, and subsequent papers). This has been found to be the case as acetylacetone and ethyl acetylpyruvate readily condense with sodiocyanoacetamide to give rise to products identical with those obtained from cyanoacetamide by Bardhan, using Knoevenagel's reagent (*cf.* also Sen and Basu, *loc. cit.*). That a trace of sodium ethoxide (as distinct from molecular quantities of it) has been found to bring about the same condensation, further proves the fundamental identity of Michael and aldol reactions.

Next an *O*-ether (V) (Claisen, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 3903) of benzoylacetone in which the ethylenic bond is fixed was prepared and its reaction with cyanoacetamide studied. The above *O*-ether reacts

with hydroxylamine (a ketonic reagent) to give rise to 3-phenyl-5-methyl-isooxazole (VI) (Claisen, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 144) as follows:

Accordingly cyanoacetamide (also a ketonic reagent) may react to form 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (VII). But on condensing the ether (V) with cyanoacetamide, the product isolated was not (VII) but its isomer 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (VIII), m. p. 310°, the formation of which may be represented in the following way:

Thus it would appear that though a substance containing a reactive methylene group be a ketonic reagent, it preferentially attacks the ethylenic linkage present in systems represented above*. This was further proved by isolating the pyridone derivative (VII), m. p. 275°-276° †, by conducting the same reaction with an isomeric ether (IX) which again normally reacts with hydroxylamine yielding 5-phenyl-3-methylisooxazole (X) (Claisen, *loc. cit.*).

* The formation of isomeric pyridones (VII and VIII) from benzoylacetone itself (Bardhan, *loc. cit.*) does not militate against the present hypothesis of preferential condensation at the ethylenic linkage as it is quite conceivable that the enolic phase is at one time set up next to the phenyl group and at another next to the methyl group.

† Issoglio (*Atti. R. Accad. Sci. Torino*, 1905, 40, 495) who obtained a mixture of the pyridone derivatives (VII and VIII) by condensing benzoylacetone with ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of ammonia found the main product (VIII, yield 76%)

The constitution of the compound (VII) is proved from the facts that on hydrolysis it gives the known 4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 413) and that it is identical with the compound obtained by condensing cyanoacetamide with acetylphenylacetylene $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{C}\equiv\text{C}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_3$ (Barat, *private communication*). Experiments on the behaviour of other *O*-ethers of β -diketones are already in progress.

The hypothesis was attempted to be critically examined from a different experimental standpoint altogether. Thus the two isomeric *C*-methylidibenzoylmethanes (the ketonic and enolic) were prepared and the condensation of cyanoacetamide with each of them was effected in the presence of Knoevenagel's reagent in aqueous—alcoholic solution as usual. In both cases the identical reaction product was isolated. This is only to be expected as in solution these isomers lose their structural individuality giving rise to an equilibrium mixture of the two isomers specially in the presence of the alkaline reagent employed. The small quantity of material at disposal precluded the investigation of the condensation in the presence of hydrogen chloride (an acid reagent) which admittedly is capable of bringing about the condensation between a carbonyl group and a methylene group (Claisen, *Annalen*, 1893, 218, 172). This however was tried with acetylacetone when no condensation product could be isolated showing thereby the inactivity of the carbonyl under such conditions and pointing to the enormous change in reactivity occasioned by enolising agencies. It should be noted here that the influence of enolising (benzene) or ketonising (alcohol) solvent does not alter the course of reaction pointing once again to the inherent tendency of such reactions to follow the course indicated above.

A passing reference may now be made as to the closure of the pyridone ring (IV). It is clear that at first a molecule of water from the aldol (III) will be eliminated leading to the formation of the unsaturated ketone (XIa) or (XIb); but preferentially (XIb) will be formed (*cf.* Lapworth and McBae, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2747; also Kon, *loc. cit.*). The formation of (XIb) is further evident from

to melt at 310° and the isomer (VII) to melt at 263° – 264° . Bardhan (*loc. cit.*) again records the melting point of the latter as 249° . These different statements led the author to repeat the condensation of benzoylacetone with cyanoacetamide when it was found that though the pyridone derivative (VIII) may be easily obtained in nacreous plates, m.p. 310° , it is very difficult to obtain the isomeric compound (VII) in a pure condition.

the fact that acetylenic ketones ($R \cdot C \equiv C \cdot CO \cdot R$) with cyanoacetamide give rise to condensation products similar to (IV) (Barat, *loc. cit.*). Next the amido-group present in (XIb) favours the formation of a dihydropyridone ring (XIII) as evident from the isolation of a compound (XIV) by Sen (*loc. cit.*). But it readily loses a molecule of water to give rise to the usual ring (IV). That the structure of the final compound is (IV) and not (XII) is confirmed by the synthesis

of 3-cyano-1:4:6-trimethyl-2-pyridone (XV) from acetylacetone and cyanoacetmethylamide (*cf. Guareschi, Atti. B. Accad. Sci. Torino, 1893, 28, 330, 337*).

In ascertaining the position of the sodium in the Michael condensation product from acetylacetone and sodiocyanoacetamide, certain interesting observations were made. Thus on methylation it yielded 3-cyano-1:4:6-trimethyl-2-pyridone (XV) which indicates that it is the *N*-sodium salt of (XVI). Consequently the reaction between

the respective pyridone derivatives (XV) and (XVII) are directly obtained as in these cases there is no chance for the formation of the ion (XXII) of the condensation product.

Finally the condensation between ethyl *cyclohexanone-2-oxalate* and cyanoacetamide is being studied in order to find whether this β-diketone yields a mixture of quinoline and isoquinoline derivatives or one single component. A compound melting at 214-215° and appearing to have the formula C₁₃H₁₄O₃N, was obtained and this on hydrolysis with fuming hydrochloric acid gave an acid, m. p. 309°. But the acid could not be converted into a simple tetrahydroquinoline derivative by heating. However, from the sharp melting point and the behaviour of cyanoacetamide on ethyl acetylpyruvate the compound may be regarded as ethyl 3-cyano-5:6:7:8-tetrahydro-2-quinolone-4-carboxylate (XXVIII) and the acid as 5:6:7:8-tetrahydro-2-quinolone-4-carboxylic acid (XXIX).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of O-Ethylbenzoylacetone, Ph·CO·CH=(OEt)·CH₃ with Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (VIII).—The ethyl ether was prepared according to Claisen's method (*loc. cit.*) and obtained as an oil with a pleasant odour, b. p. 155-157°/11 mm. An alcoholic solution of the oil (3 g.) was gradually added with shaking to a suspension of sodiocyanoacetamide prepared from 1·3 g. of cyanoacetamide in hot alcohol, and 0·35 g. of sodium also dissolved in absolute alcohol. The colour of the mixture became deeper and it was left aside. After 2 days the

hard globular sodium salt was collected, dissolved in warm water and the solution acidified when the condensation product (2 g.) was isolated. Another crop (0.8 g.) was obtained on acidulation of the mother-liquor. Crystallising the crude product (m. p. 308-306°) from glacial acetic acid with the addition of a few drops of water, 3-cyano-6-phenyl-4-methyl-2-pyridone was obtained, m.p. 310°, darkening earlier (Issoglio, *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 13.40. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

The same compound may be obtained by condensing the ether with cyanoacetamide in the presence of diethylamine as follows: Cyanoacetamide (1.8 g.) was dissolved in water by warming and the ether (3 g.) added, with just enough alcohol to effect a clear solution. About 1 c. c. of diethylamine was added and the solution was heated on a water-bath for about 45 minutes when crystals began to separate. The flask was then left overnight. Next day 3-cyano-6-phenyl-4-methyl-2-pyridone was isolated in an yield nearly equal to that obtained by Michael's reaction.

Hydrolysis of the above Pyridone Derivative.—The substance was heated with sulphuric acid (80%) for about an hour. The cooled mixture was poured into water and filtered. The filtrate on neutralisation with sodium carbonate gave a solid which on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 182-183°. (Found: N, 7.8. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.57 per cent.). It was soluble in boiling water, gave a crimson colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, and possessed all the characteristics ascribed to 6-phenyl-4-methyl-2-pyridone by Bardhan (*loc. cit.*).

Condensation of O-Methylbenzoylacetone $Ph \cdot C(OMe) = CH \cdot CO \cdot CH_3$ *with Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (VII).*—O-Methylbenzoylacetone was prepared from benzalacetone dibromide according to the method described by Weygand (*Ber.*, 1925, 58, 1478) and was obtained as a yellow oil, b.p. 147-148°/11 mm. To a cooled alcoholic suspension of sodiocyanoacetamide obtained from cyanoacetamide (4 g.) and sodium (1 g.), the ether (8 g.) was gradually added without allowing the temperature to rise. The mixture was left over for 3 days with occasional shaking. Carbon dioxide was then passed into the mixture and the precipitate was filtered and washed with water. The residue (3 g.) on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 275-76° sintering and darkening a few degrees earlier (yield, 30%). (Found: N, 13.37. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.). On repeated crystallisation

from acetic acid it was obtained in colourless prismatic needles melting at the same temperature. A mixture of this with the isomeric compound 3-cyano-6-phenyl-4-methyl-2-pyridone (m.p. 310°) melted at 247°. It dissolves in alkali but is precipitated unchanged on acidulation. It is also soluble in boiling water and acetone and imparts no colouration to alcoholic ferric chloride. The pyridone is soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid but is precipitated unchanged on dilution.

Hydrolysis : Formation of 4-Phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone.—The above condensation product was heated with 80% sulphuric acid for more than half an hour. On cooling crystals began to separate when water was added, and the product on crystallisation from dilute alcohol (charcoal) was obtained in colourless needles, m.p. 206-207° (Ruhemann, *loc. cit.*) not depressed by admixture with the compound obtained by hydrolysing 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone from the condensation product of benzoylacetone described below. (Found : N, 7.9. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.6 per cent.)

Condensation of Benzoylacetone with Cyanoacetamide.—Owing to the reason already stated, the condensation with diethylamine as the condensing agent, was effected in dilute alcohol and from the reaction mixture the main product, 3-cyano-6-phenyl-4-methyl-2-pyridone (VIII), m.p. 310° was easily isolated. Next day the mother-liquor, on acidification, yielded a product, m.p. 245-247° which was partly soluble in alcohol. The insoluble portion mainly consisted of 3-cyano-6-phenyl-4-methyl-2-pyridone whereas the crystals from the alcoholic solution melted indifferently between 248° and 255°. On recrystallisation from boiling water in which it was difficultly soluble, it melted at 263-264° (*cf. Issoglio, loc. cit.*). The melting point is raised to 273° when admixed with the compound (m.p. 275-76°) previously described. The crop, m.p. 248-255°, however, on hydrolysis with concentrated sulphuric acid (80%) yields 4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone, m.p. 206-207°, as found by Bardhan.

Condensation of Methylidibenzoylmethanes, $Ph\cdot CO\cdot CHMe\cdot CO\cdot Ph$ and $Ph\cdot CO\cdot CMe=C(OH)Ph$, with Cyanoacetamide : Formation of 3-Cyano-4 : 6-diphenyl-5-methyl-2-pyridone.—Both the methylidibenzoylmethanes were prepared from dibenzoylmethane (Diekmann, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2481). The ketonic form is more soluble in alcohol and imparts no colouration to ferric chloride solution, whereas the enol is difficultly soluble in alcohol and gives the characteristic violet colouration with ferric chloride. The two ketones (3 g. each)

were separately dissolved in alcohol and an aqueous solution of cyanoacetamide (1.1 g.) was added to each solution with sufficient alcohol to effect a clear solution. Diethylamine (4 c. c.) being added to each, they were heated under reflux on the water-bath for about 12 hours, when on acidification both the mixtures yielded the same pyridone derivative, almost in equal yield. Crystallising from pyridine with the addition of a few drops of water, it was obtained in beautiful colourless plates, m.p. 304-305°. (Found: C, 79.4; H, 5.1; N, 9.7. $C_{10}H_{14}ON_2$ requires C, 79.7; H, 4.89; N, 9.8 per cent.). The pyridone is soluble in warm alkali; and forms a crystalline sodium salt. Ferric chloride imparts no colouration to its alcoholic solution. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it but on dilution with water it is precipitated unchanged. This is converted by the action of sulphuric acid (80%) into 4:6-diphenyl-5-methyl-2-pyridone which crystallises in needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 263-264°. The latter is soluble in warm alkali and forms a crystalline sodium salt. In alcoholic solution it imparts a red colouration to ferric chloride. (Found: N, 5.65. $C_{18}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 5.36 per cent.).

Condensation of Dibenzoylmethane and Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4:6-diphenyl-3-pyridone (IV, R=Ph).—The β -diketone was prepared according to the method of Claisen (*Annalen*, 1896, 291, 52) from ethyl benzoate and acetophenone, m.p. 77-78°.

An equimolecular mixture of the β -diketone and cyanoacetamide in alcoholic solution was heated with a few drops of piperidine on the water-bath for about 3 hours, and left overnight. Next morning on acidifying the clear solution the pyridone derivative was isolated in an yield of about 40%. It crystallised from pyridine with the addition of a few drops of alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 318-320°. (Found: C, 79.25; H, 4.7; N, 10.0. $C_{18}H_{12}ON_2$ requires C, 79.41; H, 4.4; N, 10.29 per cent.). The substance is soluble in glacial acetic acid but difficultly so in other organic solvents. It also dissolves in alkali and in concentrated sulphuric acid from which solutions it can be recovered unchanged on acidification and on dilution with water respectively.

Hydrolysis: Formation of 4:6-Diphenyl-2-pyridone.—On hydrolysing the above cyanopyridone with sulphuric acid (80%) 4:6-diphenyl-2-pyridone was obtained in fine slender needles from dilute alcohol (charcoal), m.p. 207-209°. It is soluble in warm alkali and imparts a red colouration to an alcoholic solution of ferric chloride.

(Found: N, 5.8. $C_{17}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 5.66 per cent.) (cf. Meyer, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1914, ii, 90, 1).

Condensation of Ethyl Acetylpyruvate with Cyanoacetamide.—This reaction has been studied by Bardhan (*loc. cit.*). Here the condensation in benzene suspension is described. Sodicyanoacetamide prepared in the usual way was filtered, washed with cold absolute alcohol, anhydrous ether, and dried in *vacuo*. It was shaken in benzene suspension with molecular proportion of ethyl acetylpyruvate for about 2 to 3 hours and then left overnight. Next morning the benzene layer was decanted off and the sodium salt of the condensation product formed was dissolved in water. On acidifying the yellow solution ethyl 3-cyano-6-methyl-2-pyridone-4-carboxylate was obtained which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid melted at 218° . It was also soluble in boiling water and alcohol.

The condensation may also be effected by adding the ketonic ester to cyanoacetamide itself in benzene suspension in presence of piperidine.

The hydrolysis product, 6-methyl-2-pyridone-4-carboxylic acid, may be obtained by heating the condensation product with caustic soda solution (30%) for about 3 hours. The acid is soluble in boiling water, dilute acetic acid, and concentrated sulphuric acid with a green fluorescence. It begins to darken at about 270° but does not melt even at 325° . On concentrating its aqueous solution in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid long prismatic plates with a slight yellow tinge were formed which were washed with alcohol and dried in *vacuo*. (Found: N, 8.6. $C_7H_7O_3N, H_2O$ requires N, 8.2 per cent.). On heating the dry substance in a test tube, water was found to condense on the cooler part. If however the compound be rapidly heated in an electric bath or dipped into hot sulphuric acid it melts at $225-226^{\circ}$ to a red liquid.

Condensation with Acetylacetone: (i) *Formation of 3-cyano-4:6-dimethyl-2-pyridone (XVI).*—Cyanoacetamide (1.7 g.) dissolved in alcohol was added to an alcoholic sodium ethoxide (0.5 g. Na). The sodium salt was rapidly filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and dried in *vacuo*. To the sodium salt suspended in anhydrous benzene, acetylacetone (2 g.) was added with shaking. Next day the benzene layer was decanted off and on adding water and acidifying the clear solution, the known pyridone derivative, m.p. $288-89^{\circ}$ (Guareschi, *loc. cit.*) was obtained. The condensation may also be effected in alcoholic solution using molecular sodium (Michael's method) or a trace of sodium ethoxide (2% solution) as the condensing agent.

(ii) *Attempt to condense by means of Hydrochloric Acid.*—Dry hydrogen chloride (3 g.) was passed into a cooled solution of acetylacetone (1 g.) and cyanoacetamide (1 g.) in dilute alcohol. No appreciable change was observed and no condensation product could be isolated from the reaction mixture even after a fortnight. The solution was then carefully neutralized, when on adding a trace of diethylamine the solution became warm and turned red. Soon crystals (1.5 g.) of the lutidostyryl derivative, m.p. 288°, separated out.

(iii) *Formation of 3-Cyano-1:4:6-trimethyl-2-pyridone (XV).*—
(a) *By Methylating the Michael Sodium Salt.* The sodium salt formed by conducting the above reaction in alcoholic solution was filtered, washed with cold alcohol and ether and dried in *vacuo*. It (4.5 g.) was heated with methyl iodide (10 g.) and methyl alcohol (10 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 105–110° for 3 hours. Beautiful stout crystals that separated on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 203–204°. It was insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 17.3. $C_9H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 17.28 per cent.).

(b) *By Condensing with Cyanoacetmethylamide.*—Cyanoacetmethylamide was prepared by shaking ethyl cyanoacetate (30 g.) with an ounce of methylamine (33% solution) under cooling. The clear solution on concentration over sulphuric acid in *vacuo* yielded the amide (20 g.) in well crystalline form. Crystallising from ethyl alcohol it melted at 104°. (Found: N, 28.65. $C_4H_6ON_2$ requires N, 28.57 per cent.).

On adding a few drops of piperidine to a clear solution of acetylacetone (1.8 g.) and cyanoacetmethylamide (1.8 g.), the solution became warm and the colour changed to deep yellow. On keeping in a warm place (40–50°), fine crystals began to separate when it was left overnight at ordinary temperature. Next day the beautiful shining crystals (2.5 g.) were collected. They were insoluble in alkali, gave no colouration with ferric chloride, and were soluble in alcohol and boiling water; m.p. 203–204°, which was not depressed by addition of the product described under (a).

The pyridone derivative was directly obtained when the same reaction with sodiocyanoacetmethylamide was conducted in alcoholic solution.

The condensation was also carried out in benzene suspension in the following way: The sodium salt (2 g.) of the amide prepared and dried in the usual way, was taken in anhydrous benzene suspension and shaken with acetylacetone (1.7 g.). Within an hour a heavy

granular sodium compound was formed. After two days the sodium salt (8.4 g.) was collected, washed with anhydrous ether and taken in water in which it readily dissolved, but soon crystals separated out and these were found to be 3-cyano-1:4:5:6-trimethyl-2-pyridone (XV).

(iv) *Formation of 3-Cyano-1:4:5:6-tetramethyl-2-pyridone* (XVII).—The sodium salt obtained by condensing acetylacetone with sodiocyanoacetmethylamide in benzene suspension was dried in *vacuo* and heated with twice the required quantity of methyl iodide in anhydrous benzene suspension in a sealed tube at 100° for about 3 hours. The clear benzene layer was decanted off. The residual viscous mass was taken in water in which it was completely soluble. On making the solution alkaline fine silky needles separated out which on crystallisation from water melted at 179-180° and was found to be identical with the compound obtained by condensing cyanoacetmethylamide with methylacetylacetone described afterwards.

Condensation with Methylacetylacetone: (i) Formation of 3-cyano-4:5:6-trimethyl-2-pyridone.—The condensation product was obtained from methylacetylacetone and cyanoacetamide in alcoholic solution in presence of a few drops of piperidine, the yield being 75%. Crystallising from alcohol it was obtained in needles, m.p. 305-306° (Guareschi, *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 17.45. $C_9H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 17.28 per cent.). It is soluble in alkali, and is precipitated unchanged on acidification.

(ii) *Formation of 3-Cyano-1:4:5:6-tetramethyl-2-pyridone* (XVII) —The product obtained by condensing the β -diketone with cyanoacetmethylamide in the usual way crystallises from boiling water in fine silky needles, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 16.15. $C_{10}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 15.9 per cent.). It was soluble in alcohol and in other common solvents but insoluble in alkali.

Conducting the reaction with sodiocyanoacetmethylamide in alcoholic solution (Michael's reaction) 3-cyano-1:4:5:6-tetramethyl-2-pyridone was directly obtained.

Condensation of Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-oxalate with Cyanoacetamide: Formation of Ethyl 3-Cyano-5:6:7:8-tetrahydro-2-quinolone-4-carboxylate (XXVIII).—A clear solution of cyanoacetamide (2.2 g.) in water and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-oxalate (5.5 g.) (Kötz and Michaels, *Annalen*, 1906, 350, 210) in alcohol with the addition of piperidine (2 c.c.) was warmed at 60° for 2 hours when the yellow crystals

separated (1.5 g.) were collected. After adding a few more drops of piperidine to the mother-liquor it was left overnight. On acidification another crop (1.8 g.) was obtained. It crystallised from boiling amyl alcohol (charcoal), m. p. $\pm 14-215^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 11.6. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.39 per cent.). The quinolone derivative is partly soluble in alcohol and acetic acid but readily dissolves in concentrated acids and in alkalis from which it may be obtained unchanged on dilution with water and acidification respectively. Its alcoholic solution imparts no colouration to ferric chloride but exhibits a beautiful emerald green fluorescence.

Hydrolysis: Formation of 5:6:7:8-Tetrahydro-2-quinolone-4-carboxylic Acid (XXIX).—The above condensation product (2 g.) was heated with fuming hydrochloric acid (14 c.c.) at $170-180^{\circ}$ for about 4 hours. Stout crystals separated. The solid obtained on neutralising the hydrochloric acid with sodium carbonate, was crystallised from dilute acetic acid. Recrystallising from the same solvent (charcoal) it was obtained in clusters of needles, m. p. 308° , sintering earlier. (Found: N, 7.4. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 7.25 per cent.). The substance is soluble in alcohol, in alkali and also in sodium carbonate solution with effervescence, but is reprecipitated on acidification from the latter solution. The carbonyl group cannot be removed by heating the substance to its melting point as the acid itself began to decompose at that condition.

In conclusion, I wish to express my grateful thanks to Professor H. K. Sen, for his kind interest in this investigation.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

Received February 11, 1930.